

Tisbe Holothuriae T.holothuriae stationary



*Oithona rigida* temp 15–20 degrees



*Oithona rigida* temp 21–25 degrees



*Oithona rigida* salinity 15–20 (ppt)



*Oithona rigida* salinity 21–27 (ppt)



*Oithona rigida* food concentration 10,000 cells/ml



*Oithona rigida* food concentration 30,000 cells/ml



Paracyclopina nana Paracyclopina nana



Tigriopus japonicus Tigriopus japonicus



Apocyclops royi Apocyclops royi



Tisbe battagliai good diet, high food, with 100microgramsPPC



Tisbe battagliai good diet, high food, without 100microgramsPPC



Tisbe battagliai poor diet, medium food, without 100microgramsPPC



Tisbe battagliai good diet, medium food, with 100microgramsPPC

